

TRANSLATOR COLLABORATION AS A METHODOLOGICAL APPROACH IN INDIRECT TRANSLATION. A CASE STUDY ON THE TRANSLATION OF SHORT STORIES FROM UZBEK INTO MALTESE THROUGH ENGLISH

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Ensuring fidelity to the ultimate source text when working from a mediating translation requires a departure from standard binary translation models in favour of complex, multi-source and collaborative strategies. Indirect translation is prone to what Hadley (2017) called the 'concatenation effect', i.e. the tendency to omit cultural specificities and downplay the foreign origins of the original work. Hence, it is necessary for translators to employ specific methodological safeguards to bridge the gap created by the intermediary translation process. Among the methods that may be adopted to ensure fidelity, human collaboration is especially useful, particularly when the final translator (the relay-taker) lacks proficiency in the ultimate source language (Ivaska 2020). Translators may team up with native informants or subject-matter experts who provide oral explanations, literal transcriptions, or summaries of the original work to ensure cultural nuances are not lost (Ivaska 2017, Alvstad 2017). The presentation shall focus on the collaboration between the translator of the original source text and the translator of the intermediate text, specifically when the first translator belongs to the culture of the original text itself.

Based on a project consisting of the translation of short stories from Uzbek into Maltese via English, the research analyses the interaction between translators to solve challenges related to culture-specific issues and instances of ambiguity or obscurity in the intermediate text. It concludes that collaboration between translators has a double benefit: the first translator can be encouraged to reflect critically on their translation strategies and their choices, while the second translator can obtain valuable feedback to produce a higher quality translation.

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